

PRESERVATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL POTTERY TRADITIONS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF ALISHER NAZIROV'S WORK)

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Abstract: This article discusses the traditional Rishtan school of ceramics. In particular, they talked about the creative center of the International Ceramics Center in Rishtan and creative activity of master potter Alisher Nazirov. In addition, conditions have been created in our country to preserve the ancient traditions of ceramics, which are being developed as a national value, to increase its authority at the international level, and to popularize it.

Key words: Rishtan, pottery, traditional, school, circle, blue, crafts, Alisher Nazirov.

Pottery is one of the oldest crafts in human history. Archaeological finds found in various historical sites of Central Asia indicate that pottery developed in the region in the 9th-12th centuries.

In Uzbekistan, in the 19th century, representatives of historically formed traditional and non-traditional pottery arts showed an interest in the historical layers of local culture. Since ancient times, each oasis has had its own craft centers. Pottery is divided into two main types according to the production method, which are glazed and unglazed pottery. In the late 8th - early 9th centuries, glazed pottery was widespread in the cities of Maveronnahr. In the 9th-18th centuries, this style acquired artistic and high technological qualities.

In the second half of the 17th century - early 19th century, local pottery schools with their own distinctive features emerged in Uzbekistan. These are:

1. Samarkand-Bukhara school: with centers in Tashkent, Samarkand, Urgut, Bukhara, Gijduvan, Shakhrisabz, Kitab, Kattakurgan, Denov;
2. Fergana school: with centers in Rishton and Gurumsaray;
3. Khorezm school: with centers in Khanka, Madyr village, Kattabag, Chimbay.

Rishton has always been famous for its ceramics. Traditional Rishton patterns give ordinary objects a unique and unique look. The harmony of bright and charming blue-white-green colors is used for the patterns. National pottery traditions are passed down from generation to generation and continue to develop rapidly. Our opinion is confirmed by the fact that the International Ceramics Center was opened in the Rishton district. The center, which includes a museum and exhibition galleries, includes 20 separate complexes. Today, ceramic products are exported to countries such as the United Arab Emirates, the Czech Republic, Turkey, Russia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan.

The local artistic features of Rishton ceramics are often characterized by decorative patterns on products. The repertoire of its decorative complex was distinguished from other pottery schools by the richness of its colors and the richness of its patterns. Also, the entire system of patterns used in applied art was expressed in Rishton pottery. The decorative patterns of Rishton pottery consist of geometric and plant symbols, symbolic signs, object images, zoomorphic and anthropomorphic subjects. At the same time, specific subject images are depicted, from bowls, jugs, musical instruments to weapons and knives. Alisher Nazirov is one of the famous masters who has made a great contribution to the development of national

and traditional pottery. Master Rishton uses the style of decorating traditional artistic pottery objects with his own patterns and designs along with the principles of form. To date, the craftsman has created more than 10 thousand works of authorship. Since the 1990s, he has been introducing Arabic calligraphy into the decoration of flatware. At the same time, he is improving the foundations for the widespread use of the art of "alkaline glaze", which is one of the forgotten art directions, even in the present era.

His blue-turquoise patterns and designs are reflected in his works such as "Chor Gul", "Anor", "Parizog", and "Sitara", harmoniously combined in the style of Chinese painting. On his initiative, in 1997, he organized a museum workshop in the house where he lives, and has been creating his works in the direction of artistic and traditional pottery in the style of brushwork. His unique products such as "Sarshuyak", "Guldon", "Mevadon", "Dastshu", "Shokosa", "Dugusha", and "Murgoba", created on the basis of national craftsmanship, play an important role in the master's creative process.

Today, Alisher Nazirov, together with his students, continues the traditions of the Rishton pottery school, introducing the national pottery style to the world. The master has participated in many prestigious exhibitions and festivals held in our country and abroad, earning recognition from art lovers.

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